

Dermatophilosis & *A. variegatum* (Senkobo & the Tropical Bont tick)

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Dermatophilosis is a contagious cutaneous disease caused by *Dermatophilus congolensis* bacteria. Dermatophilosis is commonly referred to as "Senkobo", "rain scald", "rain rot", "lumpy wool" and "cutaneous Streptothricosis", and affects both domestic and wild mammals, including cattle, sheep, horses, zebra and antelope. In cattle, and many other species, dermatophilosis presents as an exudative dermatitis, which causes matting of the hair and scab formation. The lesions thus resemble "paintbrushes" with tufts of hair raised on a scab (Fig. 1 [1]). Lesions can be localised and of minor significance, or in severe cases can cover large areas of the body (Fig. 2), resulting in decreased productivity, suffering, and death.

Thus, not only is dermatophilosis a severe welfare concern, but the associated losses can have a significant impact on the livelihoods and food security of individual

Figure 2: Large exudative, crusty, dermatophilosis lesions on the tail head of a bovine. Image: reproduced from University of Pretoria, [AfriVIP repository](#), CC BY 4.0

Figure 1: Dermatophilosis in a bull in Ethiopia. A) lesions, B) *A. variegatum* in the rectal area. Image: reproduced from [1], CC BY 4.0

farmers and across entire regions. One study estimated the annual cost of dermatophilosis in Zambia to exceed \$3 million [2]. In Ngamiland, Northern Botswana, farmers have been suffering losses of thousands of livestock over the previous decade due to dermatophilosis, which has been attributed to *Amblyomma variegatum* (Tropical Bont tick) infestations [3].

The role of *A. variegatum* in *D. congolensis* infections

Observations by farmers and veterinarians suggesting that dermatophilosis often appears to be associated with *A. variegatum* infestation have been confirmed in several scientific studies. In Zimbabwe, herds infested with *A. variegatum* were almost 7x more likely to have clin-

ical signs of dermatophilosis compared with uninfested herds, whereas in contrast, *A. hebraeum* (South African Bont tick) infestation *did not* increase the risk of dermatophilosis [4]. In Ghana, the proportion of cattle showing clinical signs of dermatophilosis closely followed seasonal patterns in tick abundance [5]. Furthermore, acaricide-treated cattle remained free of dermatophilosis, whereas in untreated cattle the number of lesions was related to the number of *A. variegatum* infesting the cattle [5].

The long mouthparts of *A. variegatum* (Fig. 3) may act

Figure 3: Female (L) & male (R) adult *A. variegatum* ticks. Image: [Daktaridudu](#), CC BY-SA 4.0.

as mechanical vectors, but this does not explain the association with *A. variegatum* only, since all *Amblyomma* spp. have similarly large mouthparts. Neither does it explain the frequent observations of lesions on body parts not infested by *A. variegatum*.

Tick-induced immunosuppression

A. variegatum appears to facilitate infection via systemic tick-induced immunosuppression [6]. This explains the severity of lesions in tick-infested individuals [7], and lesions on body parts not infested by ticks [5]. Early studies explored this in both naturally-infected and experimental herds, yielding similar findings. More recent studies have shed light on the potential mechanisms of immunosuppression and the potential differential role of nymphs *vs.* adults.

Note that *D. congolensis* is also pathogenic in the absence of *A. variegatum*, and factors other than *A. variegatum* infestation such as warm, wet weather, play a role in its epidemiology (for example, "rain scald" is a common condition in equids in temperate regions where *A. variegatum* are absent).

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